

Experimental

Palladium(II) chloride (Johnson Mathey) was used. Benzene (AnalaR) was purified by freezing and then distilling over phosphorous pentoxide and glacial acetic acid (B.D.H.) was distilled over potassium permanganate. The electronic spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 554 spectrophotometer.

Results and Discussion

In the electronic spectra a common band appears at 277 nm for all the complexes recorded in benzene, whereas in acetic acid this band appears at 256 nm without affecting the charge transfer band. Each complex exhibits two bands, one for intra-ligand transition and the other due to ligand-to-metal or metal-to-ligand charge transfer transition. The band at 277 nm in benzene and that at 256 nm in acetic acid are assigned as $L(\pi) \rightarrow L(\pi)^*$ transition. The other intense band is assigned as ligand-to-metal or metal-to-ligand charge transfer band. Appearance of these two bands at $6\,000\text{--}9\,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in C_6H_6 and at $10\,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in AcOH shows that they are in *trans*-configuration and the observed data are in good agreement with the reported spectral studies^{1,3,4}.

The large bathochromic shifts of the charge transfer bands (332 nm to 363 and 365 nm) in the complexes *trans*-PdCl₂(*p*-OH.C₆H₄.SCH₃)₂ and *trans*-PdCl₂(*p*-OCH₃.C₆H₄.SCH₃)₂ are due to the presence of electron-repelling OH and OCH₃ groups in *para*-position of the ligand. The shift is more in *trans*-PdCl₂(4-OCH₃-3-CH₃.C₆H₃.SCH₃)₂ than in *trans*-PdCl₂(4-OCH₃-3-CH₃.C₆H₃.SCH₃)₂ and exerts an accelerating influence of the conjugation of methoxy group with the phenyl ring. The probability of attaining planarity of methoxy group with aromatic ring increases due to the presence of methyl group at 3-position. There can, therefore, be enhanced resonance interaction of the methoxy group with the aromatic ring, resulting in a greater mesomeric electron release to the sulphur of SCH₃. Similar trend was also observed⁵ with chloramine-T oxidation of phenyl methyl sulphoxides. Bathochromic shifts are also observed in the *p*-Cl, *p*-Br and *p*-I substituted complexes. This is obviously due to the presence of SCH₃ in *para*-position to Cl, Br and I groups. Here, SCH₃ is an electron-acceptor and there is a possibility of the expansion of the valence shell of sulphur atom. Similar observation was reported⁶ in the nmr studies of some substituted phenyl methyl sulphides. The charge transfer bands of the complexes, *trans*-PdCl₂(*o*-NO₂.C₆H₄.SCH₃)₂, *trans*-PdCl₂(*p*-NO₂.C₆H₄.SCH₃)₂, *trans*-PdCl₂(*o*-COOH.C₆H₄.SCH₃)₂ and *trans*-PdCl₂(*p*-COOH.C₆H₄.SCH₃)₂ and those of the ligand bands absorb almost at the same frequency. In such case the directional charge transfer might have been opposed by the electron-withdrawing nature of these substituents in the phenyl ring. The OCH₃, NO₂ and COOH groups in *meta*-position cause hypsochromic

shift due to the electron-withdrawing effect. Methoxy group in *ortho*-position causes a bathochromic shift due to enhanced resonance which outweighs its inductive effect. Two CH₃ groups cause steric inhibition in *trans*-PdCl₂(2,6-di-CH₃.C₆H₃.SCH₃)₂ complex which results in hypsochromic shift. The symmetry of sulphur *p*-orbitals requires that in the polar excited form of methyl sulphide, the sulphur-methyl single bond should lie in the same plane as the benzene ring. *Ortho*-substituents would therefore be expected to inhibit sulphur-benzene conjugation. Steric inhibition of resonance is also observed in *trans*-PdCl₂(3,5-di-CH₃-4-OCH₃.C₆H₂.SCH₃)₂.

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Polarographic Study on the Complexation of Praseodymium with some Amino Acids

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THE present study reports the stability constants of the Pr^{III} complexes with glycine, L-glutamine and L-asparagine in order to determine the effects of sizes and steric hindrances of amino acids on the solution stability of the complexes.

Experimental

A.R. grade chemicals were used. The concentrations of metal, potassium chloride and gelatin in the test solution were 2.0 mM, 1.0 M and 0.01% respectively. A pH of 2.40 ± 0.1 was adjusted with dilute solutions of sodium hydroxide and hydrochloric acid, and was measured on a LI-10 needle type pH meter. Current-voltage measurements were made on a manual polarograph using a Toshniwal

PL-50 polyflex gelvanometer. The capillary characteristics were: $m=2.18 \text{ mg s}^{-1}$ and $t=3.0 \text{ s}$ at 40.0 cm (39.98 cm) effective height of mercury¹. The study was carried out at 25 and 35°.

Results and Discussions

Pr^{III} gives a well-defined three-electron reversible reduction wave in KCl and gelatin². The nature of waves of metal and its complexes were reversible and diffusion-controlled as revealed from the straight lines plots of $\log i/(i_a-i)$ vs $E_{d,e}$ and i_a vs \sqrt{h} respectively. Lingane's method³ confirmed the formation of 1 : 1 complexes of Pr^{III} with all the three ligands at 25 and 35°. The values of stability constants are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF Pr^{III} COMPLEXES OF THE LIGANDS AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

pH = 2.40 ± 0.1, $\mu = 1.0 \text{ M}$ (KCl), $E_{1/2} = 1.81 \text{ V}$ vs S.C.E.

Ligand	log β	
	25°	35°
Glycine	4.40	3.70
L-Asparagine	3.50	3.10
L-Glutamine	3.45	2.60

The trend of stabilities of complexes is L-glutamine < L-asparagine < glycine. As the size of amino acid increases the stability of complexes decreases⁴. The lesser stability of L-glutamine than L-asparagine complexes is due to the greater steric hindrance in the former. The higher stability of glycine complexes is well-known⁵.

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Studies on Mixed Ligand Complexes of Dioxouranium with Salicyl Hydroxamic Acid

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A resume on salicylhydroxamic acid (SHA) enlightens its analytical use where its coordinating behaviour is found to be limited to the formation of 1 : 2 complexes with various oxometal ions¹. The present communication deals with the preparation and characterisation of some mixed chelates of dioxouranium(VI) with SHA of the type, $(\text{NH}_4)_2[\text{UO}_2\text{L}_2\text{X}_2]$, $n\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{NH}_4[\text{UO}_2\text{L}_2\text{Y}, \text{H}_2\text{O}]$, $n\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $[\text{UO}_2\text{L}_2\text{B}]$, $n\text{H}_2\text{O}$, where L is the deprotonated mono-anion of SHA, $\text{X} = 1/2\text{CO}_3^{2-}$, $1/2\text{SO}_4^{2-}$, $1/2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$; CH_3COO^- , NO_3^- , Cl^- ; $\text{Y} = \text{Br}^-$, I^- ; $\text{B} = 1,10\text{-phenanthroline (Phen)}$, $2,2\text{-bipyridyl (bipy)}$, $\text{CO}(\text{NH}_2)_2$; and $n = 0-3$.

Experimental

SHA was prepared by the reported method². All other reagents were of A.R. grade.

Preparation of $(\text{NH}_4)_2[\text{UO}_2(\text{L})_2\text{X}_2], n\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{NH}_4[\text{UO}_2\text{L}_2\text{Y}, \text{H}_2\text{O}], n\text{H}_2\text{O}$: To an aqueous solution of uranyl nitrate hexahydrate (~0.002 mol) the ammonium salt (0.005 mol) containing X or Y anion was added with constant stirring to obtain a clear solution. A solution of SHA (0.006–0.008 mol) in either 2 : 1 acetone-water or in acetone was added to it with constant stirring. The precipitate appeared either immediately or on stirring for a long time. The resulting yellowish orange to reddish brown crystals were filtered, washed with warm water, ethanol or acetone and finally dried in a vacuum desiccator over concentrated H_2SO_4 (yield 60–80%).

Preparation of $[\text{UO}_2\text{L}_2\text{B}], n\text{H}_2\text{O}$: Uranyl nitrate hexahydrate (0.002 mol) in ethanol or methanol was mixed with phen/bipy (B; 0.006 mol) in the same solvent. To the resulting suspension SHA (0.006 mol) in 1 : 1 acetone-water was added with constant stirring to obtain a red solution. A reddish brown/yellowish red precipitate separated on long stirring was dried as before (50–70%).

The estimation of uranium, nitrogen, halogens and other physicochemical measurements were done according to the procedure described in our previous work³.

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